

Self-Determination Theory in Sport: Differences between Athletes in Individual and Team Sports

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Abstract

The purpose of this study was to examine the relationships between needs satisfaction measures and motivational differences for athletes in individual versus team sports using self-determination theory. Participants were 260 college athletes from the University of New Mexico. Needs satisfaction measures predicted intrinsic motivation among both types of athletes. In line with predictions, extrinsic motivation was positively correlated with relatedness and negatively correlated with autonomy. We also found that there was not a relationship between sport and type of motivation, which indicated a similar pattern of motivation for individual versus team athletes.

Self-determination theory (Deci & Ryan, 1985; 2000) explains the conditions that either assist or hinder the natural processes of healthy psychological development (i.e., well-being) and optimal motivation (i.e., intrinsic motivation). SDT proposes that people who are intrinsically motivated will engage in the most self-determined behavior, and self-determined behavior in turn fulfills three underlying needs for competence, autonomy, and relatedness (Deci & Ryan, 2000). It may be the case that different types of motivation are important when looking at sports participation and success, both because individuals may differ in how they fulfill their needs and because different sports may support different types of need satisfaction. We predicted that motivation would differ by sport. We also predicted that needs satisfaction measures would be positively correlated with intrinsic motivation.

Procedure

Participants were 260 division one college athletes from the University of New Mexico (49% male, 51% female) from 11 different teams. Participants completed a battery of assessments at one of their scheduled practices. The assessments included questions on present and future motivation to participate in their sport and questions on needs satisfaction.

Needs Satisfaction & Motivation

	Intrinsic Motivation	Extrinsic Motivation	Amotivation
Competence	.12*	.01	-.19**
Relatedness	.36**	.08	-.18**
Autonomy	.23**	-.117	-.29**

* $p < .05$, ** $p < .01$

Discussion & Conclusion

A difference in motivation between team and individual sport athletes was not found. However, a difference in needs satisfaction was found. Individual athletes have more autonomy which would suggest they are more self-driven in their sport. Results indicated that athletes in different sports are equally motivated regardless of the sport that they are participating in. The lack of motivational differences between individual and team athletes was surprising. One explanation is that if an athlete is motivated and wants to do well, the type of sport is inconsequential. Another explanation is that individuals self-select into the sports that are a good physical and psychological fit, and thus are best suited to meet their needs.

Callahan, T. J., Bryan, A. D., & Magnan, R. E. (2023). Self-determination theory in sport: Differences between athletes in individual and team sports. *Journal of Sport Psychology*, 45(1), 1-10.